

THE ESSENCE OF CREATIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10598065>

Annotation: This thesis discusses the pedagogical foundations of the development of creative thinking of elementary school students in the educational process. Discussions of researchers-scientists on the development of creative thinking are also presented.

Key words: intensive development, creativity, primary education, observation, comparison, reproductive level, neuro-physiological activity.

Introduction.

The analysis of the communicative nature of education, the development of such principles, methods and forms of designing educational and cognitive situations that suggest the organization of didactically appropriate, highly effective joint activities of teachers and students come to the fore.

In many countries of the world (the USA, England, France, Germany, etc.), the study of creativity problems is being conducted particularly intensively. The results of these studies were both empirical findings and hypotheses and concepts, which deserve the greatest attention of modern teachers. The very concept of creativity is significantly revised. A number of authors (S. Stein, A. Rotenberg, K. R. Hausman, A. Hutson, etc.) gave a definition of creativity, which means any innovation. At the same time, they emphasize that this new social and personal value should be useful (R. Stein). "We hypothesized that creative activity and innovation have criterion characteristics" (A. Rotenberg and K. R. Hausman).

In recent years, many groups of foreign philosophers, sociologists, psychologists and teachers have intensified the study of creativity problems. These groups generously subsidize various Monopolies and concerns. In particular, research on the problem of creativity has been conducted for decades. The phenomenon is studied from different positions: theories of individual creativity are developed, creativity and creative thinking are studied, attempts are made to develop the conceptual apparatus of the concept under consideration.

According to many scientists, creativity is more or less characteristic of everyone: a person is distinguished by the desire to express himself, strive for novelty, implement new, original ideas. An important component of personal

creativity is the desire to act, create something new, and above all, active action.

According to the works of A. Bodo, J. Burre, G. Leputra, R. Remusham, R. Mato, L. Schwartz, a creative person is a person who does not know peace. He is not very disciplined, questions many things, is curious and has wide interests. Often, he has a sense of humor and can even laugh at himself, he has a sense of beauty. In most cases, a creative person does not depend on his own judgments, but tries to make others conform to his vision of the world. He knows exactly what he knows and what he does not know, it is this quality that guides his work, raises questions, leads to discoveries. A creative person is able to agree with a new effective idea, even if it contradicts his views, but at the same time he is independent enough to not accept the point of view of others. knows how to work.

We found that the process of human development is carried out in a self-developing educational system consisting of structural and functional elements and having an energy source, using a systematic approach, we distinguished creativity as an element of the system. It is necessary to define the concept of creativity, show its importance in modern conditions, and consider the possibility of its development among students-subjects of the educational system.¹

The state of intensive development of the child's body.

During the primary school age, the skeletal system of students still has many things at risk, there is significant muscle development, but it is weak and the child gets tired easily. The brain weight of a primary school student reaches 90% of the brain weight of an adult. Its functional improvement process continues.

The noted characteristics of neuro-physiological activity determine the primary school student's emotionality, lack of self-control and inability to control actions. Such excitement easily destroys the nervous system. Children get tired quickly, especially from monotonous activities. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to changing the types of activities during the educational process and organizing rest. Monotonous forms of education and upbringing are absolutely unacceptable in primary classes. A proper sleep pattern is also important. 7-8-year-old children should sleep 11 hours, and 9-10-year-old children should sleep at least 10 hours a day.

Regular enrichment of knowledge, formation of new skills and abilities

¹ Вяткин Л.Г.,Тарский Ю.И. Психолого-педагогические основы развития креативного потенциала обучающихся (Акмеологические аспекты). - Саратов,- 1994,- 92 с.

leads to rapid quality education for the knowledge activity of a primary school student. In order to manage this activity, it is necessary to keep in mind the characteristics of perception, attention, memory and thinking of a primary school student.

Attention - attention of a primary school student is distinguished by some features - active attention, directing the mind to what he perceives, imagines, thinks and speaks. Attention is a very complex cognitive process. It is involuntary and arbitrary in terms of activity, and narrow and wide in scope. The following properties are known: switching, distribution (concentrated and distributed); strength and stability (strong, weak, stable, unstable). Compulsive attention prevails in elementary school students. Bright, colorful things, an interesting story will immediately cause an emotional response. Voluntary attention is not well developed. This is due to the lack of development of the regulatory function of the second signaling system. Children have a short attention span, which means they cannot take in a large number of things at once. Distribution of attention - paying attention to different objects for a long time causes certain difficulties. As a result of increased sensitivity, children easily move from one object to another. Elementary school students are distracted: they don't see what is easy to look at, make gross unforgivable mistakes, etc.

At school, the child enters a group with a completely different character than the group in kindergarten. Pupils are united with activities of serious social importance, and this creates favorable conditions for the formation of socialization as their personal characteristics. But this process continues in its own way. 1st-2nd graders still have a poor perception of their commonality in their relationships with the class, they do not understand the relationship between their behavior and the behavior of their peers. Their actions happen not together, but in close proximity. They are not very interested in the success of their friends, they often complain about each other. At the same time, children like to participate in the social life of the class and school, they willingly respond to the following tasks with clear goals: planting a lot of trees in the alley, coming up with a poem in a fairy tale, diligently performing daily tasks - cleaning the classroom, duty, etc. k. Later, they begin to consider themselves a part of the whole, are interested in the success of their peers, knowledge indicators. Cases of complaining to each other are rare.

During this period, students evaluate the moral qualities of their friends. If the teacher skillfully guides primary school students, the formation of new

personal characteristics will continue successfully. In elementary grades, the teacher's grades are taken for granted. Schoolchildren have not yet formed the skills of self-organization of behavior. They willingly respond to the teacher's demands, accept his help. This explains a very important shortcoming in the management of classroom teams. Teachers often act as direct organizers of school work and pay little attention to working with assets. As a result, favorable conditions are not always created for the development of the self-management system. Significant changes occur in the concept of friendship of elementary school students. Initially, such relationships begin under the influence of external conditions: usually children who sit at the same table or study in the same class become friends. But as he grows older, the child begins to pay more and more attention to the moral qualities of his comrades and friends. He pays attention to how principled, honest, friendly, faithful and other characteristics they are. A friendly relationship begins to be built on the basis of unity of moral characteristics. Its content becomes more complicated: friendships are strengthened not only during free time, but also during joint study and extracurricular activities.

Friendly communication enriches the child with social experience and deepens the sense of socialization. Teachers and leaders should create favorable conditions for the development of students. Properly organized games and socially useful works are of great importance in this. In particular, there is no substitute for various school games: role-playing, sports, etc., they help to form many important personal qualities, responsibility, discipline, organization. Little by little, primary school students' interests, especially cognitive interests, are becoming more diverse and meaningful. If in the early stages of education, children are more interested in the learning process itself, then the vehicle is the content of cognitive activity. They like to participate in conducting experiments, creating visual aids. Children love not only fairy tales, adventure literature, but also books that reveal the heroism of the war years, stories and stories about their peers. They are interested in international life events, sports, science and technology achievements. At the same time, children have instability and diversity of interests. Today, let's say, a boy likes to collect stamps under the influence of his philatelist, and tomorrow he is an athlete: he is interested in judo wrestling. Teachers and parents should pay close attention to the development of sustainable interests.

A number of features leave a mark on the character of a primary school student. First of all, it is an emotion, new things, events cause vivid feelings, an

intense response. Children do not know how to control themselves, emotions are shown very directly on the outside. In addition, they appear quickly and are easily replaced by others or vice versa. In the process of education, it is necessary to remember the emotional weakness of the child. Teachers and parents should take into account the features of the primary school student's will. He does not tend to think about his actions for a long time, does not know how to control himself, does not engage in difficult activities. Any assignment should therefore include a number of specific immediate goals. Complex activities should be divided into separate stages and strictly control their execution.

In general, dynamism is observed in the character of elementary school students. There is a complex process of forming a person's personality. Thus, we can conclude that the pedagogical conditions for the development of creative thinking of elementary school students depend not only on the developmental characteristics of elementary school students, but also on the organization of the educational process, its structure and content, as well as the tools used in the lesson and affects the readiness and readiness of the teacher to work with these educational tools.

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